

Epiverse-TRACE Summit Report

Strengthening Sustainable and Inclusive Analytics Ecosystem for Epidemic Preparedness

2–6 December 2024 | Banjul, The Gambia

1 Preface

The **Epiverse-TRACE Summit**, held from **2–6 December 2024** in **Banjul, The Gambia**, marked a significant milestone in advancing inclusive, open-source outbreak analytics. Hosted by the **Medical Research Council Unit The Gambia at LSHTM**, the event convened 44 participants from Africa, Latin America, and Europe, including representatives from LSHTM (UK); Pontificia Universidad Javeriana and Universidad De Los Andes (Colombia); World Health Organization (WHO); and Data.org. It was the third in-person convening of the initiative, aimed at reviewing progress and setting strategic priorities for the next phase.

The summit reaffirmed Epiverse-TRACE’s mission to build a robust, equitable, and sustainable ecosystem for epidemic intelligence, grounded in collaboration and local ownership. This model of global health innovation leverages high-quality open tools and inclusive training to support data-driven decision-making, especially in low- and middle-income settings.

Prior to the summit, a five-day **training course** on *Outbreak Analytics and Applied Modelling with R* was conducted from **25–29 November 2024**. Facilitated by MRCG, LSHTM, and Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, the course trained 29 participants from 15 African countries and piloted the **Epi Training Kit (EpiTkit)**. The training was well-received and served as a springboard for summit discussions on capacity building.

The event opened on **Monday** with a ceremony led by the **Minister of Health of The Gambia** and featured the **pre-launch of Epiverse Phase 2** and a presentation by Data.org. **Tuesday** featured reflections on lessons learned thus far, and sustainability and inclusivity of the Epiverse ecosystem. **Wednesday** offered team-building activities to strengthen collaboration across regions and disciplines.

On **Thursday**, sessions focused on how Epiverse tools could be used in smaller than usual outbreaks, neglected tropical diseases (NTDs), One Health, and national surveillance systems. These discussions highlighted both the tools’ potential and practical challenges of implementation in these diverse contexts.

The summit concluded on **Friday** with a review of the pre-summit training. Feedback was overwhelmingly positive, and participants discussed plans to **scale up training** efforts—adapting materials regionally, supporting local trainers, and embedding modules in national public health curricula.

Throughout the week, the summit highlighted the initiative’s growing impact and reinforced shared commitments to participatory governance, open science, and global collaboration. The **Epiverse-TRACE Summit 2024** represents a turning point in the effort to democratize epidemic intelligence through inclusive, transparent, and sustainable approaches.

Bubacarr Bah, PhD
Head of Data Science, MRCG
MRCG PI in Epiverse-TRACE

2 Introduction

Powered by [Data.org](https://data.org), the Epiverse-TRACE project has made substantial progress toward producing analytics tools aimed at addressing the most critical questions during epidemics. Currently, up to **fourteen (14) Epiverse-TRACE packages** are available on [CRAN](https://cran.r-project.org/). This reflects the results of two years of joint efforts between team members and our user communities.

Every year, the Epiverse-TRACE team members, along with invited stakeholders from WHO, Data.org, and various healthcare organizations, convene to discuss progress, evaluate deliverables, and plan future activities. The third Epiverse-TRACE annual summit was held at the MRC Unit in Fajara, The Gambia from December 2 to 6, 2024, under the theme: **Strengthening Sustainable and Inclusive Analytics Ecosystem for Epidemic Preparedness**.

This annual flagship event brought together 44 participants, including Epiverse-TRACE teams, with 6 members from LSHTM, 4 members from Universidad Javeriana and Universidad de los Andes in Colombia, 6 members from the MRC Unit The Gambia, and 5 members from data.org.

3 Opening Ceremony

The Honorable Minister of Health of The Gambia, Dr. Ahmadou Lamin Samateh, officially opened the summit, on the morning of 2nd December 2024 at Sir Dawda Kairaba Jawara International Conference Center.

Dr. Ahmadou Lamin Samateh (left photo), **Minister of Health of The Gambia**, speaking at the opening ceremony of the **Epiverse-TRACE Summit**, emphasized that *“the development of analytics tools for pandemic preparedness and response is both timely and essential”*.

Dr. Davis Nwakanma (left), **Chief Operations Officer at MRCCG**, gave remarks on behalf of the MRCCG Director. He was joined by **Dr. Uyi Stewart** (center), **Chief Data and Technology Officer at data.org**, and **Dr. Bubacarr Bah** (right), **Head of the Data Science Cluster at MRCCG at LSHTM**. Each shared their perspectives, expectations, and hopes for the project.

Dr. Bah highlighted that **Epiverse-TRACE** is a global initiative dedicated to developing **open-source tools** that aim to transform how data science is applied for social good. He emphasized that the initiative seeks to shift the use of analytics in global infectious disease response from **ad hoc solutions** to **integrated, generalisable, and scalable software**—driven by the community and designed for long-term impact.

Dr. Stewart pre-launched Epiverse Phase 2 during which he expressed his excitement about what has been achieved in Phase 1 and what Phase 2 is about to bring to Africa. He used this opportunity to update partners on the Phase 2 implementation plans. **Danil Mikhailov, PhD** President and CEO of data.org, and other data.org staff joined the event virtually.

4 Pre-Summit Training

Course: Outbreak Analytics & Applied Modelling with R

Group photo of training participants and facilitators

The Epiverse-TRACE initiative hosted its first African training course on “Outbreak Analytics and Applied Modelling with R” from 25–29 December 2024 at MRCG in Banjul, The Gambia. Facilitated by experts from MRCG, LSHTM, and Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, the course aimed to build participants’ technical capacity in using R for outbreak data analysis and modeling. It received 151 applications, from which 29 participants across 15 African countries were selected. Notably, 35% of attendees were women, reflecting a strong commitment to diversity and inclusion.

Over five days (about 40 hours), the course provided a balanced mix of theoretical foundations and practical application. Participants engaged in interactive coding exercises, group discussions, and case studies, gaining hands-on experience with real-world epidemiological data. The training helped strengthen regional capabilities in outbreak analytics and laid the groundwork for future collaboration within the Epiverse-TRACE network.

A detailed report of the training is available on Zenodo: [Epiverse Training Report](#).

5 Sustainability of Epidemics Analytics Tools Ecosystem

This session explored strategies for sustaining software analytics tools and ensuring their ongoing development and usage. The discussion concentrated on four critical areas and their associated challenges: financial sustainability, community development, governance structures, and branding initiatives. The key insights from each area are summarized below.

Financial sustainability

Approach: Combine external funding with internal lobbying to sustain financial support.

Funder Priority: Funders seek impactful projects, particularly those with measurable software tool adoption.

Impact Measurement Framework

Quantitative Metrics: Track downloads and usage statistics

Qualitative Metrics: Assess actual usage patterns and effectiveness.

Integration: Connect usage data with training programs.

Support: Data.org will assist in defining appropriate metrics.

Key Challenges

Stakeholder Misalignment: Different impact measures matter to academics, Research Software Engineers (RSEs), and funders.

Transparency Gap: Need clear communication about how impact will be measured so team members can contribute effectively to achieving these goals.

Community

Two Distinct Groups:

- *New comers:* trainees learning new approaches.
- *Existing community:* academics & package maintainers with established practices.

Challenge: Context collapse when communicating across these different audiences

Community Building Principles

Communities strengthen when organized around shared purposes and activities like training, development days, and outbreaks response coordination.

Training-Centered Approach

Continue to develop Epiverse open-access training materials and actively sought involvement of teams with non-TRACE packages

- Build community identity around training activities
- Training collaboration will drive necessary development work (interoperability, standardization)

Organic Development Structure

Package ecosystem structure should include: training materials, vignettes, and how-to guides.

Governance

We need to establish governance frameworks for:

Technical governance

- Determine who is willing to maintain when current maintainers leave
- Determine the procedure for allowing or removing “hobby” maintainers
- Select board members that would take the executive decisions

Financial governance: Determine who can bring funding to the project

Social governance: Describe procedures on how to handle users concerns

Branding

Define the core brand identity by

- writing brand brief (what does the brand evoke, what does it represent, what does it make people feel)
- building shared understanding by creating unified primary branding language
- identifying brand audiences
- localizing secondary branding language to the different brand audiences to increase relevance
- tailoring messaging to each audience’s context and priorities

It is to be noted that data.org showed willingness to take a back seat in the governance of Epiverse and to allow it to be more community driven. Therefore, further discussions on the sustainable governance of Epiverse by team members were recommended.

6 Inclusivity within Epiverse-TRACE Tools Ecosystem

Ms **Khairoonisa Foflonker** from Stellenbosch University gave online presentation titled “**Demystifying Inclusivity**”, in which she explored embedding diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) into research and development practices. She emphasized that true inclusivity requires understanding power dynamics and cultural sensitivity, with researchers and healthcare practitioners acknowledging their authority while engaging communities as partners.

Foflonker highlighted how contextual privilege creates a “**luxury of obliviousness**” that perpetuates inequalities. Structural barriers like visa restrictions and funding disparities exclude researchers from developing countries and marginalized groups. She distinguished between operational DEI (short-term compliance efforts) and strategic DEI (long-term cultural transformation integrated with organizational mission).

The presentation concluded that meaningful inclusion requires challenging systemic barriers rather than symbolic gestures, fostering inclusive leadership, and creating environments where all voices are valued. Foflonker urged participants to reflect on their roles in sustaining or challenging existing structures.

7 Team Building

The third day of the summit was dedicated for team building activities. From the thrill of the Kartong Snake Farm to the rhythm of paddles on the River Gambia, our team-building journey blended adventure, culture, and collaboration. The below images highlight some experiences aimed at strengthened team members' trust, communication, and camaraderie.

8 Potential Use Cases for Epiverse-TRACE Tools

This session focused on the potential integration of Epiverse-TRACE tools within the One Health framework—a collaborative, multi-sectoral approach that acknowledges the interconnected health of humans, animals, plants, and their shared environments. The discussion explored how these tools could strengthen cross-disciplinary surveillance systems and enhance outbreak preparedness and response.

Key challenges within the One Health context include:

- Population growth and geographic expansion
- Climate change and land-use transformation
- Increased global movement of people, animals, and animal products
- Rising threats from zoonotic, neglected tropical, and vector-borne diseases
- Pressing issues such as antimicrobial resistance, food safety, and environmental contamination

8.1 Potential Role of Epiverse-TRACE Tools

Currently, Epiverse-TRACE tools are primarily focused on human health, though they hold potential for adaptation to animal and environmental health contexts. Opportunities worth exploring include:

- Developing proactive outbreak scenario models to support preparedness within the One Health framework by adapting existing human-centered planning tools.
- Fostering interdisciplinary collaboration through partnerships with veterinary and environmental sectors to broaden the tools' applicability.
- Enhancing cross-sector awareness of Epiverse-TRACE's capabilities and limitations to facilitate more integrated use across health disciplines.

8.2 Feedback from group discussions

Insightful discussions were held which raised both concerns against and recommendations for extending applicability of our tools to One Health. The main reservations included our limited expertise and resources to fully integrate One Health into Epiverse-TRACE at this stage as well as data availability and structural differences (e.g., herd vs. individual tracking) may pose challenges. On the other hand, discussants also recommended low-effort involvement/engagement at this stage maybe possible by prioritizing tool extensibility to accommodate future One Health needs (rather than developing from scratch), maintaining the project's core mission while fostering collaborations and exploring interoperability with other “verses” for holistic insights including the One Health community.

Conclusion & Future Steps

Conclusion

While immediate integration of One Health into Epiverse-TRACE tools is constrained by scope/resource and data challenges, the initiative holds promise for future expansion. Strategic steps include raising awareness, fostering partnerships, and adapting tools for broader use, ensuring alignment with the project's goals and resources.

Future Steps

- Identify low-effort applications/adaptations (e.g., readepi, cleanepi, visualization tools).
- Engage with the community including veterinary and environmental experts, for example, by participating in regional and global One Health meetings.
- Pilot interoperable solutions to bridge human-animal-environment health analytics.

9 Outbreak Analytics Training

Training is a cornerstone of the Epiverse-TRACE project, ensuring that our advanced analytics packages are recognized and adopted by a broader community. As the project enters its second phase, the focus shifts towards developing and delivering structured courses. Training within Epiverse-TRACE is facilitated through a variety of resources, including showcases, case-studies, how-to guides, tutorials, and the Epi Training Kit [EpiTkit](#). During the final day of the summit, participants shared insights on designing an in-person data-centered outbreak analytics course aimed at training and teaching outbreak analysis as well as on the translation and adaptation of the Epi Training Kit materials for the African context. The discussion also reflected on lessons learned from previous training sessions, identified existing gaps, and explored strategies to address them. In this session, the training team presented the pre-summit training report along with its feedback see [Pre-summit Training report](#).

We also discussed strategies for implementing training in the project's second phase, including the EpiTkit modules as part of comprehensive training in TRACE-LAC for Latin America and the LSHTM-MRCG plans for delivering training courses in Africa. The discussion centered on four key aspects of training: content, audience, cultural adaptation, and assessment. Participants, divided into four groups, responded to targeted questions within each aspect. Their insights were collected and summarized in the following boxes.

Content

The course should be designed as an integrated, flexible, and adaptable training program, allowing for self-paced learning while remaining easy to follow. Focus on merging and re-emerging infectious diseases, vector-borne diseases, and non-communicable health challenges. Key examples include Ebola, Mpox, HIV, Malaria, Chikungunya, Dengue, Marburg virus disease, and cervical cancer caused by HPV.

Audience

Encourage ongoing, inclusive feedback by offering multiple channels—such as in-person or virtual input, anonymous surveys, real-time comments, and discussion forums—while also engaging focus groups, diverse participants, and local leaders to ensure all perspectives, especially underrepresented ones, are heard and addressed.

Cultural Adaptation

Customize course materials for each training session by respecting regional, cultural, and religious differences; promote inclusivity through culturally aware content, inclusive language, and a clear code of conduct that fosters respect and avoids reinforcing bias or discrimination.

Assessment

Conduct ongoing evaluations through surveys, interactive games, and practical exercises to assess learning and engagement; foster sustained stakeholder involvement via platforms like GitHub and group discussions to gather both structured and qualitative feedback for continuous improvement.

Summit Participants from Epiverse Collaborative

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